

Energy System Modelling Using OSeMOSYS

Development of a national energy system model – Activity 1

Please use the following citation for:

- **This Activity**

Plazas-Niño, F. (2024, April). Energy System Modelling Using OSeMOSYS: Development of a national energy system model – Activity 1 (Version 1.0).

- **OSeMOSYS UI Software**

Climate Compatible Growth. (2024). MUIO (Version v5.0.0). GitHub. <https://github.com/ClimateCompatibleGrowth/MUIO>

- **OSeMOSYS Google Forum**

If you are stuck, please ask questions [here](#). If you get ahead, please answer questions in the same forum. Please state that you are using the 'OSeMOSYS UI' and not 'ClicSAND'.

Tasks

1. **Approaching modelling deliverables:** Read the document '**Project Overview**' to understand the different activities to be developed throughout the project. Then, read the following paper [\[link\]](#), which serves as a benchmark for the paper structure to be developed by each of you. Please note that our work will be more simplified and will not include such a detailed analysis as carried out in that paper.
2. **Country selection:** Select one country based on your research objectives. Please consider the availability of data in part 3 when making your choice.
3. **First Data Collection:** Once you have selected your country to be modelled, proceed to gather the following data using any online resources:

- National Energy Balance
- Historical Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (at least the last 10 years)
- Vehicle Fleet Data (number of vehicles by type for a recent year or historical)
- Historical Installed Capacity of Electric Generation by Technology (or at least one recent year)
- Historical Electric Generation by Technology (or at least one recent year equal to the installed capacity data)
- Historical Electric Generation with Hourly Resolution (or at least one recent year)
- Reserves of Fossil Fuels (coal, oil, natural gas, uranium) if applicable
- Estimated Maximum Potential of Solar, Wind (onshore and offshore), Biomass, Geothermal, and Hydroelectric Electric Generation (if available)